

EXCISE TAX: GENERAL AND SPECIAL

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Annotation: The thesis explores the economic essence, peculiarity, fiscal significance of the excise tax, and also developed proposals for improving the excise tax.

Keywords: tax system, taxation, excise tax, excisable goods, tax rate, customs duty, sales tax

Аннотация: В тезисе исследуются экономическая сущность, особенность, фискальное значение акцизного налога, а также разработаны предложения по совершенствованию акцизного налога.

Ключевые слова: налоговая система, налогообложение, акцизный налог, подакцизные товары, налоговая ставка, таможенная пошлина, налог с продаж

Issues of improving the taxation system and tax administration in our country, including the excise tax collection mechanism, are important today. Since 1992, when the excise tax was introduced in our republic for the first time, there have been continuous debates about the purpose of its collection, its amount, import of goods, including from the CIS countries, as well as the procedure for calculating and collecting the tax. Therefore, researching the main areas of improvement of excise tax in our republic and developing solutions to controversial issues in this regard is appropriate only from the point of view of research and analysis of theoretical factors of indirect taxation and tax administration, as well as world experience.

It should be noted that excise tax is recognized as an effective form of indirect taxation in a number of countries at different stages of economic development. At the same time, the excise tax is currently successfully used in the practice of world taxation. The main reason for the prevalence of excise tax from ancient times to the present day is its fiscal importance and high level of collection. Even in 1666, the French economist F.Demezou emphasized this: «Excise alone is capable of providing all other tax revenues and more»¹

The term «excise», according to a number of researchers, comes from the Dutch word *exijs* (Old French *accise*), which means «assessment for the purpose of taxation». There is also the following opinion, that is, the word «excise» is derived from the Latin word *accidere* (to cut off, to cut), which meant a notch on

¹Malov V.N., Colbert J.B. Absolutist bureaucracy and French society. -M.: «Science», 1991. P.90

a special stick used to measure the amount of drink contained in a container for taxation purposes.

Excise tax is a type of indirect tax imposed on consumer goods (services) of mass type, which is set as a surcharge on the price of the product (or service tariff) and thus is charged to the final consumer.

Excise duties are essentially divided into individual and universal excise duties. Individual excise duties are similar in essence and nature to universal excise duties - value added tax, sales tax but differ from them in that they are imposed on a limited group of goods. Generally, excise goods are of a general nature, and the demand for these goods is low elastic (elastic) with respect to the level of income.

Excise tax is one of the first to be introduced during the transformation of the economy, because it is relatively easy to introduce this tax and control over its payment. Such administrative advantages arise from the ability of tax authorities to control the physical volume of certain goods expressed in kind, instead of relying on accounting books for tax collection.

Historically, excise tax was considered a tax on production rather than consumption, that is, it was levied on producers at the place of production. The fact that the excise tax is set at a fixed amount per product unit or as a percentage of the value of the product further complements the administrative advantage of the tax. In addition, excise tax, especially when calculated against a unit of administrative expenses, can bring high revenue if the group of excise goods is carefully considered and includes a limited group of goods.

The main difference of the excise tax from other consumption taxes and compulsory payments: firstly, the specificity of their scope - application to the consumption of a specific good (service) or group of goods (services), and secondly, they are non-equivalent. The first feature distinguishes the excise tax from consumption taxes, which have a broad taxation base like value added tax or sales tax, and the second feature distinguishes it from various fees and charges paid for the use of public goods and services.

Excise tax can be divided into three main groups based on its performing functions: the first group includes traditional excise tax (on alcoholic beverages and tobacco products). Excise tax collection in this group mainly has two goals: limiting the consumption of socially harmful products and fiscal, the second group includes excise taxes on oil and petroleum products, and the third group includes excise taxes on luxury items, which usually do not have a clearly focused fiscal goal. Excise tax in such a group performs a redistributive function

in most cases, since the consumer of these goods is a wealthy segment of the population. In addition, the following other goals can be mentioned, for example, by imposing an excise tax on luxury goods (cars, expensive electronic products, etc.) in some countries on capital-intensive production products, stimulating labor intensive industries, by introducing an excise tax in addition to customs duties on imported goods, it is possible to encourage domestic producers or improve the foreign trade balance.

A transition economy can benefit from a judiciously designed excise tax system, as excise taxes can generate a significant amount of tax revenue in the early stages of transition.

Organization of the excise taxation system is relatively simple and increases the experience of the tax authorities in working with the transaction goods traded within the framework of the market economy. Such experience helps to form the basis of the complex methods of audit and control necessary for working with value added tax and income tax. Thus, the excise tax, on the one hand, provides financial income necessary to overcome the difficulties of the transit period while the economy is developing, and on the other hand, it helps the tax authorities to move to new and more perfect methods of taxation.

At the end of our research, we found it permissible to make the following suggestions for improving the mechanism of excise tax collection, including:

- The application of excise tax to goods that are considered social damage or cause negative consequences has certain positive aspects. Such taxation serves to limit the consumption of goods with a certain dangerous potential, for example, in alcoholic beverages and tobacco products, or in the consumption of gasoline or other types of fuel that pollute the environment. Such indirect benefits create additional tax efficiency, but most excise taxes are usually (and should be) introduced to generate tax revenue;
- It is necessary to introduce an excise tax on energy drinks (energy drinks with high caffeine content) and non-alcoholic soft drinks with high sugar content produced in the Republic of Uzbekistan and imported into the customs territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- In accordance with the tax legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, excise tax is included in the price and value added tax base. Based on this, when taxpayers import excise goods into the customs territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the amount of customs duty and excise tax is taken into account in the basis of value-added taxation. In our opinion, the mechanism of tax collection is slightly distorted here, that is, excise tax and customs duty amounts

are also included in the value added tax base. That is, the amount of excise tax already collected is included in the taxable base, which means paying tax again for the tax paid. This is inconsistent with the principles of accuracy and fairness of taxation.

The implementation of the above-mentioned proposals and considerations will allow the use of excise tax as a means of regulating consumption and stimulating production, accelerate the process of improving the excise tax in the context of economic liberalization, and create the basis for an increase in budget revenues through the establishment and development of national production.

